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European forum and oBServatory for OPEN science in transport

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D6.1 Project logo and website

Final

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Executive summary

The present deliverable is part of the WP6 “Dissemination and Engagement”, and the first output of T6.1 “Dissemination strategy and tools”. It presents and describes the BE OPEN logo and the Transport Observatory/Forum for Promoting Open Science logo, hereafter TOPOS, and the project website.

This document is divided in three sections: the introduction, the logos and the website.

The “INTRODUCTION” briefly introduces the objectives of the WP6 “Dissemination and Engagement” and how the logos and the website will contribute to it.

The Section 2, “LOGOS” presents and describes the BE OPEN main and variation logos and the usage guidelines. As a project outcome, it also foresees the characteristics of the TOPOS logo, which will be developed at a later stage.

The Section 3, “WEBSITE” presents the BE OPEN project website, delineating its structure and content, implementation, evolution throughout the project life and maintenance.

Disclaimer:

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

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Abbreviations

Abbreviations	
CMS	Content Management System
T	Task
TOPOS	Transport Observatory/Forum for Promoting Open Science
WP	Work Package

1 INTRODUCTION

The present deliverable is part of the WP6 “Dissemination and Engagement”[1], which has as objectives:

- Disseminate key project outputs to key actors and transport stakeholders;
- Implement and regularly update an appropriate online presence (web-site, social media, EOSC integration) and other relevant dissemination material to ensure continuous outreach of the project outcomes, as well as transfer of knowledge;
- Organise project key events and ensure cooperation with the most important international forums, as well as liaise with related projects and initiatives. Demonstrate the economic viability and lay the foundations for subsequent exploitation;
- Engage publishing companies and set up communication tools/actions;
- Supervise project results and key outcomes through an external Advisory Board, consisting of internationally renowned experts.

To create awareness and achieve the objectives above stated, the consortium has defined under T6.1 “Dissemination strategy and tools” [1], the development of the BE OPEN project logo and TOPOS logo and the implementation of the project website. These elements will be presented and described in the present deliverable.

2 LOGOS

2.1 BE OPEN logo

The BE OPEN logo has been developed by VDI/VDE, partner of WP6, with support of ECTRI.

The logo presented on Figure 1, sets the ground for the BE OPEN brand by visually translating the project’s scope and vision:

- The **transport research** is represented by the modes/means of transport;
- The sphere stands for a lens representing the **transparency, openness, fairness and reproducibility of science**;
- The dots and intersecting lines represent the **knowledge shared and developed through collaborative networks**.

Figure 1. BE OPEN logo (primary version full color)

i. Logo usage guidelines

The BE OPEN logo will be used across all communication and dissemination materials. For this purposes, the primary logo version (Figure 1) should be used whenever possible, following the guidelines below.

Text font: EliotSans-Bold

Text color codes: HEX code : #052b35

RGB code (5, 43, 53)

CMYK code (91%, 19%, 0%, 79%)

The BE OPEN logo is also available in color and gray scale versions, for use in white and dark backgrounds, see ii. Logo variations.

The logo versions in multiple high-resolution file types are available for partners use under the BE OPEN Freedcamp project management tool, together with the logo usage guidelines to assure consistency and quality use.

ii. Logo variations

Figure 2. BE OPEN Color logo with text for dark background

Figure 3. BE OPEN Color logo without text for dark background

Figure 4. BE OPEN B&W logo with white text for dark background

Figure 5. BE OPEN Color logo without text

Figure 6. BE OPEN B&W logo dark text

Figure 7. BE OPEN B&W logo without text

2.2 TOPOS logo

As an exploitation result of BE OPEN, the TOPOS (Transport Observatory/forum for Promoting Open Science) will have an identity of its own while keeping a strong link to the BE OPEN/mother-project. Therefore, the TOPOS logo which will be developed at later stage in the project will be an adaptation of the BE OPEN logo.

3 WEBSITE

The project website is the central element of the project's dissemination strategy. It is designed to be the main tool to communicate and disseminate the knowledge produced by the project and make it available to the appropriate audiences. It presents the project concept and plans and will be continuously updated throughout the project duration to incorporate the step-by-step outcomes and outputs of the project.

3.1 Design and development

The website is designed to be informative yet straightforward with clear language to ensure wide communication with diverse categories of stakeholders and external audience. Its design privileges an easy-to-follow menu with dynamic content - images and diagrams, in addition to text. Furthermore the responsive design approach will allow the website to dynamically adjust to the size of the screen on which it is displayed (computer, tablet, smartphones...).

The website follows the project identity, in terms of logo, colors and typography in order to create a coherent link between all the planned communication tools.

3.2 Structure and Content

3.2.1 Header and footer

The website header (Figure 8. Website header) is visible in all pages and includes the BE OPEN logo, the menu, the search, the project's social media icons and Partners area, which is linked to the BE OPEN Freedcamp project management tool. The menu is organised in six tabs with no subtabs, for an

easy and straightforward navigation.

Figure 8. Website header

The website footer (Figure 9. Website footer) also visible in all pages includes the project contact form, acknowledgement of EU funding, the privacy policy, the cookies policy and license/copyright. It also features the registration form for the BE OPEN newsletter.

Figure 9. Website footer

The project

Scope

Open Science is a modern movement that represents a new approach to practicing science, in a way that increases openness, integrity and reproducibility of research. It aims at making scientific process and results more transparent and accessible at all levels and to everyone. The rapid growth of digital technologies and new collaborative tools become enablers of Open Science, allowing to speed up the process of adopting open habits and facilitating the sharing of large volumes of information, study materials and data. Europe has the culture and ability to share research activities across national boundaries, which along with its remarkable research and knowledge base, put it in a leading position in the world to promote and expedite the new Open Science way of working.

As the way in which science and research are carried out has changed, BE-OPEN project aims to assist in operationalising Open Science in transport research at the European level, through a series of targeted coordination and support activities. BE-OPEN is a 30-months H2020 Coordination and support action started on 01 January 2019, and addresses the call MG-4-2-2018 Building Open Science platforms in transport research.

Objectives

BE OPEN aims to promote Open Science in transport research and assist in regulating and standardizing it. The overarching vision of BE OPEN is to create a common understanding on the practical impact of Open Science and to identify and put in place the mechanisms to make it a reality in transport research.

[See the specific objectives](#)

Expected impacts

- Develop **governance and new operational/business models** for enhancing OS by describing the rationale of how to create and capture value in economic and social context
- Develop the **European Code of Conduct on OS** in transport proposing recommendations and proper guidelines that allow setting up a community of transport research organizations
- Create of **awareness and visibility** (authorities, Industrial and SMEs, Associations in Transport, Publishing Companies, and the various ETPs, and strong media coverage)
- Engage **international stakeholders** in mutual learning and sharing experiences
- **TOPOS forum and observatory** tools to contribute to create a **solid knowledge base on the implementation of OS** approach in transport research

Methodology

The overall BE OPEN methodology follows a systematic implementation solution that depicts the different activities to be implemented for fostering Open Science in transport research as well as the interrelations among them.

[Read more](#)

Figure 11. Website "The project" page

3.2.4 News

This page shows the project related news, in regards to activities, events and publications and also external key developments under the project scope. It will be updated throughout the project duration. It can display up to 30 news on one page.

News

Figure 12. Website "News" page

3.2.5 Events

The Events page lists the project event and other relevant ones organised by partners and external stakeholders in relation to Open Science in Transport. It displays both the upcoming and past events. For each event, more information like date, place, agenda, registration, logistical information, map, but also presentations and pictures will be made available. It will be updated throughout the project duration each time a new event is scheduled.

Events

Figure 13. Website "Events" page

3.2.6 Publications

This page is the library for all the public deliverables and materials of the project. It will be updated throughout the project duration. All the documents will be available for download.

Publications

Figure 14. Website "Publications" page

3.2.7 Partners

The Partners' page presents the 17 Consortium members and 8 Third Parties, with hyperlinks to their respective institutional webpages. This page also presents the BE OPEN Advisory Board.

Partners

BE OPEN brings together a strong partnership comprising leading transport research institutions and research networks at pan-European level, covering all transport modes (i.e. road, rail, water, air), and partners with high level expertise in Open Science practice who are at the forefront of relevant developments in Europe, complemented by an advisory board of world-leading experts engaged in international initiatives.

Consortium

Figure 15. Website "Partners" page

3.2.8 TOPOS

The TOPOS page is the first introduction to the expected output of the BE OPEN project the TOPOS - Transport Observatory/Forum for Promoting Open Science - its expected impact, functionality and resources.

TOPOS

TOPOS stands for Open Science in Transport Observatory and Forum

BE OPEN will design and develop TOPOS (Transport Observatory/Forum for Promoting Open Science), a collaborative effort from key partners in transport research promoting territorial and cross border cooperation.

TOPOS will have two major components:

- **TOPOS forum** which will capture and present the common culture and practices of data stewardship in transport research.
- **TOPOS observatory** the aim of which is to showcase the status and progress of open science uptake in transport research. This will be a collaborative effort with OpenAIRE which is currently developing a European Open Science Observatory, and will be based on existing efforts, i.e., the Open Science Monitor Framework developed in the EOOSC pilot project, the DG-RTD Open Science Monitor³, FAIR tools⁴, TRIMIS⁵. The new TOPOS observatory will follow the specifications of the Open Science Monitor Framework with the proper modifications to the difficulties and the complexity of promoting Open Science in transport. In this end, new schemes for membership and governance will be utilized and a portal area will be included to gather all research results.

Figure 16. Website "TOPOS" page

3.3 Implementation, updates and maintenance

3.3.1 Implementation

The BE OPEN website has been developed by an external provider, TypiDesign, chosen on the basis of the “best value for money” offer received. From six communication agencies contacted, three have responded to the request for quote for the development of the BE OPEN website, but also of the newsletter, leaflet and roll up banner.

The website is registered under the domain name **beopen-project.eu** at Gandi, and booked for 10 years. Other options of domain names were explored but many (like be-open.eu) were already booked.

The website was built in TypiCMS, an open source CMS developed by the selected web developer, accessible on desktop and mobile displays. This content management system was chosen for its clear interface, ease-of-use, lower set up cost, flexibility and capacity to support numerous media types.

The website is indexed under the relevant project keywords and performance measured by Google Analytics.

3.3.2 Updates and maintenance

The website updates, to what concerns all new content, under the developed layouts, will be done by ECTRI. Any additional need of structural update or change will be requested to the outsourced web developer.

In terms of maintenance, the web developer will be responsible for the operational support until September 31, 2021 (3 months after the project end). ECTRI will be in charge to keep the website online and updated until December 31, 2021 (6 months after the project end) and the domain name active for at least 10 years after the project end.

4 REFERENCES

[1] BE OPEN Grant Agreement